

METHODOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF TEACHING NEW GENERATION TEXTBOOKS IN PRIMARY CLASSES BASED ON THE SKILLS OF THE "4 K" MODEL

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Abstract. *Improving the quality of education is an important factor in making children interested in reading; study the best experiences of foreign countries in the field of education; giving more importance to children's critical thinking, free expression of their own opinion.*

Keywords: *innovative process, inquisitiveness, creativity, paper-pencil, blackboard, communication, teamwork, creativity, critical thinking.*

Introduction

"The cornerstone of development and the force that makes the country powerful and the nation great are science, education and training," said Shavkat Mirziyoyev, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. All stages of this sector are being radically reformed and comprehensively developed, and the fourth priority direction in the Development Strategy of our country is aimed at the development of the education sector and human capital. Accordingly, the year 2023 was named "Year of attention to people and quality education". On December 29, 2022, at the International Congress Center, the President said, "Improving the quality of education is the only right way to develop New Uzbekistan!" he got acquainted with the exhibition of modern textbooks on the subject. An important factor in improving the quality of education and making children interested in reading is, first of all, creating a good textbook.

In the concept of development of the public education system until 2030, approved by the Decree of the head of our state No. 5712 dated April 29, 2019, the tasks of improving the teaching methodology were defined. Accordingly, for the past four years, work has been carried out on updating textbooks, and a special working group has prepared textbooks for grades 1-4 on the basis of advanced foreign methodology. It is being adapted from the original version with a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 international license. Before introducing the new innovative approach in the schools of Uzbekistan, the best experiences in the field of education of foreign countries such as Singapore, China, England, Finland, Estonia were studied and students were taught "4K: 21st century vision that includes the principle the main attention was paid to the development of skills.

In the education of countries with high international rankings, such as PISA and PIRLS, special emphasis is placed on communication, research, creativity, which includes the "4K" principle, and therefore they achieve great results in international is reaching rankings.

Materials and Methods. Today, the rapidly changing and constantly developing information industry, as well as the modern lifestyle of a person integrated with the high speed of industrial and information development of the whole humanity, creates a high demand for the development of a new person and personality. Market demand leads to constant updating of collective skills, professions and specialties. Education is being contextualized, so human competence limited to only one area of life is not enough. Today, it is important to have meta-competencies based on different mental activities (for example: collective intelligence, empathy, etc.).

In 2002, an American non-governmental non-profit organization called the Partnership for XXI Century Skills was established to determine the most important competencies needed by an individual and to bring together leading business groups to study their potential development paths. It brought together leading business groups to explore their own development paths. Also, 4K Communicative (communication, communication) for graduates of educational institutions; Collaboration - cooperation, teamwork; Creative thinking (creativity); Educational leaders creating the concept of critical thinking: National Education Association of the United States, United States Department of Education, AOL Time Warner Foundation, Apple Computer, Inc., Cable in the Classroom, Cisco Systems, Inc., Dell Computer Corporation, Microsoft Corporation, SAP, Ken Kay (President and Co-Founder), and Deans Golder-Dardis. The 21st century labor market demanded competitive and in-demand skills.

Search results. The 4K Model: As a Tool for Measuring Critical Thinking, Creativity, Communication, and Collaboration - Adopted by the academic community, the 4K concept has been extensively researched and tested, resulting in its widespread use in many educational standards. In 2010, the American Management Association confirmed the relevance of the 4K concept in its research. Now, what is 4K education? Why does our child need this and where can we learn with this system? Let's try to find answers to these questions. 20 years ago, no one would have even dreamed of the existence of such professions as SMM specialists or mobile application developers. In the age of the labor market, it is impossible to know exactly which professions will be needed in a few years, but it will certainly change. Not to mention manual work, the work of accountants and analysts will also be automated. It's safe to say that future employers will be interested in flexibility and skills that cannot be replaced by algorithms alone. As for the theory, in 2016 the president of the World Economic Forum, Davos Klaus Schwab, announced the beginning of the fourth technological revolution. According to him, now robots will do all the work for us, and by 2020, every worker who considers himself necessary should know the following: the ability to solve complex tasks; critical thinking skills; creative thinking; ability to manage people; ability to work with a team; the ability to identify and control other people's feelings and their own; able to express one's opinion and judge and make decisions; adapt to the customer; ability to enter into a contract; the ability to quickly switch from one task to another.

In 2015, the critical thinking and creative abilities of the person who took the 4th and 10th places will be among the three most needed by 2020. It was decided to call these flexibilities Soft Skills (flexible skills, professional competence) and Hard Skills - "strict" professional skills. In our country, experts in the field of education reduced the first ten of Davos to four main skill systems and then gave it the name "4K system": Collaboration (Coordinator) (Coordination) (sotrudnichestvo) teamwork; Communicative (Communication), (dialogue); Creative thinking (creativity); Critical thinking (Kriticheskoe mishlenie) (CriticalThinking). If we give a separate explanation to each "K", Critical (critical) thinking (Kriticheskoe mishlenie) is the ability to control the flow of information, see cause-and-effect relationships, sift out unnecessary information and summarize. Decision making in case of failure and understanding the reasons for its successes and failures. Creative thinking (creativity), (Kreativnost) - allows you to behave confidently in changing situations, make unconventional decisions, evaluate the situation from different points of view. A creative person becomes a producer. He can develop and improve other people's initiatives. Overcoming difficulties becomes an interesting puzzle for him. Communicability (communication), (communication) - today, everyone is a phone call or a day away, that is, 24/7, or an SMS away. The ability to conduct negotiations and establish communication, listen to the interlocutor and express one's point of view becomes a life skill. Collaboration (Coordinator) (Coordination) (sotrudnichestvo) teamwork is closely related to

professional competence. The ability to assess the common goal and its results, to define roles on the way to its achievement.

Discussion. The field of education has become an ideologically important topic of modern developed and developing countries. All literate people know well that the quality of education is a powerful force that paves the way for the future of the country and is the basis for its stability. Each older generation, looking for ways to transfer the accumulated knowledge and experience to the next generation, developed different ways and means of learning and teaching. Knowledge is eternal only if it is written with a pen and put on paper. Spreading knowledge to the general population is a source of goodness. The responsibility of education is also very wide. Tools created in production help to solve these tasks. There are many educational tools available. If we dwell on the most important of them, we can talk about paper-pencil, blackboard-chalk, computer, smart equipment. It's no secret that we are so skeptical about the effectiveness of computers in education, because many people admit that it is difficult to imagine the field of education without these tools. It was not easy for teachers to master the computer. Our level of development is still low. One of the shortcomings in the teaching activity of mankind, formed over thousands of years, was observed. On the basis of highly developed production technology and market relations, the image of the present time has changed a lot. In the past, the teachers of the society acquired certain knowledge, skills and qualifications up to a certain age and taught the next generation. The need to develop knowledge and skills fund will not be in great demand. The reason for this is that technology, people's lifestyles, tools do not change much.

Conclusion. It is gratifying that our society is capable of accepting and mastering any innovation, new project, new technology that appears in the world, and has large financial resources. That is why we want the main strategies in the field of education to be based on the development of traditional teaching methods that increase the student's ability to think and provide quality education, along with mastering new technologies. It is clear that it is necessary to master new technologies, but during the process we noticed that they are only suitable for helping the teacher as simple tools such as paper, pencil, blackboard and chalk. If we not only need to take into account the development, but if we are not very careful in using smart technologies, if we do not create sanitary-hygienic standards for their use in the lives of students, if we do not establish strict control, "Internet addiction", Dangerous factors such as "addiction to the Internet" and "addiction to ICT games" also threaten the child's psyche. We cannot solve these factors with a total ban. We need to think about making wise decisions that combine the child's potential and the possibilities of technology by setting limits on the time he can work with various devices in accordance with sanitary and hygienic standards. Also, what are the conditions for the new model to work well? The innovative approach based on the "4K" model does not require special conditions for use in schools. For example, students develop critical thinking skills through quizzes, and communication skills through quizzes and exercises. It is wrong to say that there are no conditions for using these methods in schools. Previously, we paid more attention to the writing of boalas, we wrote them in written speech. With the new experience, children's critical thinking and free expression of their opinion are more important. Students learn to approach problems from an analytical point of view and form their own point of view based on logical thinking.

REFERENCES

1. Akhmetova G.K., Karaev Z.A., Mukhanbetzhanova S.T. Methodology of organizing teacher training when electronic education is introduced. Almaty: OJSC "BAO "Orleu", 2012. 418 p.
2. <http://smart.orleu-edu.kz/>
3. <http://zkoipk.kz/>